

Learning Cycle 7E Learning Model and Acid Base Learning Outcomes of Students of SMA Negeri 1 TINAMBUNG

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Abstract:

This quasi-experimental study evaluates how the Learning Cycle 7E model enhances acid-base learning outcomes for class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung. This study used a posttest-only control group design to compare the learning outcomes between the experimental and control groups. The participants were all students from class XI MIA at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung. Class XI MIA 3 was the experimental group and Class XI MIA 4 was the control group. Observations during the study revealed the effects of the LC 7E learning method, it was carried out actively and went very smoothly. In the descriptive analysis, the experimental group's

average score was 78.11, while the control group averaged 72.40. Inferential statistics revealed that the data were neither normally distributed nor homogeneous, so the Mann-Whitney test was applied with $\alpha = 0.05$. From the results of this test, $Z_{hitung} > Z_{tabel}$ ($2.94 > 1.96$) was obtained, the results suggest that the LC 7E learning model significantly impacts the learning outcomes of class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung on acid-base topics.

Keywords: *Learning Cycle 7E, Learning Outcomes, Acid-Base.*

Introduction

Education is a way to prepare the next generation who are intelligent, wise and loyal to lead the country. In Law no. 20/2003 concerning the National Education System states that education is the process of organizing learning activities, creating safe and supportive learning conditions, and helping students develop their abilities, skills, intelligence, self-control and potential (Rasinus et al., 2021)

Chemistry learning is a teacher's effort to teach chemistry and its use in everyday life. Learning objectives can be realized through the use of strategies, methods, techniques and models in teaching and learning activities (Hamalik, 2008). Learning chemistry requires a deep understanding of the concepts that have been acquired so that they can be remembered for a long time. So as a teacher you must be able to adopt strategies, methods or learning models so that students can study well and understand the chemistry concepts being taught.

The results of interviews with chemistry teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung revealed that one of the chemical materials that is classified as difficult is acids and bases. Acid-base material has a wide range of material and requires in-depth knowledge. Acids and bases have material that is conceptual and computational. Chemistry teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung tend to still use it *Direct Instruction* or direct learning. So that students are still used to information obtained directly from the teacher as the main source.

Direct instruction teaching that focuses on the teacher (teacher center). Teachers play an active role in delivering material and teaching it directly to students. This direct instruction model can take the form of demonstrations, exercises or practices, group work, lectures and so on. (Susanti et al., 2017). In this model, the teacher provides ideas or concepts to students directly while still paying attention to the various phases of learning. In Jamil's explanation, direct teaching involves giving instructions to students which are delivered directly by the teacher (Jamil, 2013).

Observations at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung show that student performance in chemistry, particularly on acid-base topics, is suboptimal, as reflected in their daily scores, more than 60% of all students have not yet received a minimum completion criteria score (KKM), namely 78. When the teacher presents learning material, students are classified as inactive during the lesson being delivered and only sitting quietly without anyone responding to the teacher. Based on this, it is concluded that student learning outcomes in chemistry learning activities tend to be low.

Acid-base learning material that applies the model *problem-based learning* From previous research, there are still indicators of learning outcomes that have not been completed, namely determining which indicators will be used to determine the acidity level by observing how the indicator color changes in different solutions (Wulan, 2020).

Based on the problems above, regarding the learning process which tends to be low and

indicators of learning outcomes that have not been completed in learning acid-base material. One learning model that focuses on students, namely the learning model *Learning Cycle 7E*, is one model that researchers are trying to apply to help improve student learning outcomes. A statement from Eisenkraft (2003) states that this is a learning model *Learning Cycle 7E* divided into seven phases: *Elicit* (raise students' initial knowledge), *Engage* (gives ideas), *Explore* (conducting an investigation), *Explain* (explain), *Elaborate* (does explanation), *Evaluate* (evaluate), and *Extend* (expand). (Dermidag, 2011).

The 7E Learning Cycle model consists of the following phases: **Elicit**, where students are prompted with basic questions to activate prior knowledge about the upcoming lesson; **Engage**, in which the teacher introduces the learning plan, motivates the students, and stimulates their thinking; **Explore**, where students investigate and build their own understanding through observation, discussion, and inquiry; **Explain**, where students articulate the concepts they have grasped from their exploration; **Elaborate**, in which students deepen their knowledge by applying it to problem-solving; **Evaluate**, where the teacher assesses the students' understanding; and **Extend**, where students integrate the newly acquired concepts with other relevant knowledge to tackle more complex problems.

Widoratih et al. (2016) found that using the Learning Cycle 7E model improved student learning outcomes. Apriani (2012) shows that general science skills and student learning outcomes The Learning Cycle 7E model can enhance learning activities, students are expected to participate actively, creatively and directly in teaching and learning activities that will apply the learning model *Learning Cycle 7E*. Based on this, researchers are interested in carrying out research with the title "The influence of learning models *learning cycle 7E* on the learning outcomes of class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung on the main material of acids and bases"

Research Methods

This research was conducted in December-February 2024 at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung, in Polewali Mandar Regency, West Sulawesi Province. This research uses Posttest-Only Control Design as the research design. Post-test will be given in the design Posttest-Only Control Design to ensure students' learning objectives. The study involved randomly assigning two classes: the control group used traditional teaching methods, while the experimental group followed the Learning Cycle 7E approach. Research design Posttest-Only Control Design (Sugiyono, 2011), presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Posttest-Only Control Design

Note: R₁: Experimental Group; R₂: Control Group; T₁: Treatment with the Learning Cycle 7E model; T₂: Treatment without the Learning Cycle 7E model; O₁: Post-test results of the experimental group; O₂: Post-test results of the control group

This study's population consisted of all students from class XI MIA at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung for the 2023/2024 academic year, who were divided into four classes. From the results of a simple random technique (simple random sampling) two classes were randomly selected, namely class X MIA 3 as an experimental group consisting of 32 students and class X MIA 4 as a control group consisting of 32 students.

The variables analyzed in this study include independent and dependent variables. The independent variable is the use or non-use of the Learning Cycle 7E model, while the dependent variable is the learning outcomes on acid-base

topics for class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung. Data was collected via a post-test with 25 multiple-choice questions, each with one correct answer. This post-test aims to assess the students' final abilities in each class.

The data were analyzed descriptively to summarize student achievement in classes using the 7E learning cycle model, and inferentially to extend findings from the sample to the population.

Results

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis aims to summarize the chemistry learning outcomes of class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung on the acid-base topic, comparing experimental and control groups. The results for class XI MIA 3, using the Learning Cycle 7E model, and class XI MIA 4, using direct instruction, are shown in Table 1

Table 1. Description of Student Learning Outcomes in the Experimental Group and Control Group

Statistics	Statistical Value	
	Experimental Group	Kelompok Kontrol
Sample	32	32
Lowest value	41,66	41,66
The highest value	87,5	87,5
Average value	78,11	72,40
Mode	84,65	84,70
Median	83,25	80,05
Standard Deviation	10,14	14,31

Table 1 shows the value that students got in the experimental group and control group which refers to the level of completion of chemistry learning outcomes. Student learning outcomes classified based on the completeness category for each indicator can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Criteria for Completeness of Student Learning Outcomes

Value	Completeness Criteria	Experiment		Control	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frekuensi	Presentase
≥78	Complete	22	68.75%	14	43,75%
<78	Not Completed	10	33.34%	18	56,25%
Amount		32	100%	32	100%

Table 2 shows that students in the experimental group, taught with the Learning Cycle 7E model, achieved better learning outcomes than those in the control group, who received instruction through the direct instruction model. When

categorized based on the completion criteria indicators, Table 3 shows the learning outcomes percentages for both the experimental and control groups.

Table 3. Categories of Completeness and Percentage of Achievement of Each Indicator

No	Indicator	Experiment		Control	
		Percentage	Note	Persentase	Ket
1	Explain a number of substances that are acidic or basic based on their characteristics in everyday life	95.87%	Complete	94,78%	Complete
2	Describe the different concepts of acids and bases.	84.37%	Complete	78,12%	Complete
3	Explain the concept of acids and bases according to Arrhenius, Bronsted-Lowry and Lewis and draw conclusions.	83.65%	Complete	81,24%	Complete
4	Explain the meaning of acid and base indicators	96.87%	Complete	81,25%	Complete
5	Identify the properties of acid and base solutions by applying a number of indicators	82.09%	Complete	78,9%	Complete
6	Examine natural materials suitable for use as indicators.	84.30%	Complete	78,12%	Complete
7	Analyze the correct indicators to identify the acidity (acid or base) of a solution	85.41%	Complete	58,53%	Not Completed
8	Determine the pH of solutions for strong acids, strong bases, weak acids, and weak bases with known concentrations.	64.58%	Not Completed	49,99%	Not Completed
9	Determine the Ka of a weak acid or the Kb of a weak base from its concentration and pH.	52.08%	Not Completed	48,9%	Not Completed

Table 3 reveals that the experimental group shows higher completeness in learning outcomes for acid-base solutions compared to the control group.

The observation of student learning on acid-base material using the Learning Cycle 7E model, conducted by two observers, showed a "very good" implementation percentage. Details of the application in the experimental class are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Observation Results of the Implementation of the Learning Model (Learning Cycle 7E) in the Experimental Class

No	Aspek	Rata-Rata Persentase	Kategori
1	Pendahuluan	90%	Very high
2	Elicit	50%	High
3	Engagement	75%	High
4	Explore	100%	Very high
5	Explain	83,3%	High
6	Elaborate	87,5%	Very high
7	Evaluation	100%	Very high
8	Extend	83,3%1	High
9	Penutup	75%	High

Interventional Statistical Analysis

The study tests how the Learning Cycle 7E model affects student outcomes, analyzed through inferential statistics. However, before testing the hypothesis, prerequisite tests, including normality and homogeneity tests for both the experimental and control groups, are conducted. These two tests serve as assumptions for hypothesis testing.

Normality Test

The distribution is considered normal if the calculated Chi Square value is less than or equal to the value contained in the Chi Square Table ($\chi^2 \leq \chi^2_t$). Results are abnormal if they exceed ($>$) (Sugiyono, 2011). In the experimental group are $\chi^2 = 50,05986$ values for χ^2_t at the confidence level (α) = 0.05 and degrees of freedom (dk) = 3, the value is $\chi^2_t = 11.07$. Value ($\chi^2 > \chi^2_t$) then it can be concluded that the data is not normally distributed. Meanwhile, in the control group, the calculation results in was obtained $\chi^2 = 21.40214$. value for χ^2_t at the level of trust (α) = 0.05 and degrees of freedom (dk) = 3, we get the value $\chi^2_t = 11.07$. Value ($\chi^2 > \chi^2_t$) then it can be concluded that the data is not normally distributed.

Homogeneity Test

The criteria for homogeneity testing are with a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$, namely when $F_{\text{count}} < F_{\text{table}}$, then the data is homogeneous (Subana, 2000). The homogeneity test shows $F_{\text{count}} = 1.98$ and $F_{\text{table}} = 1.84$ at the 0.05 confidence level. Since F_{count} exceeds F_{table} , the variances between the experimental and control groups are from non-homogeneous populations.

Hypothesis Testing

Since the learning outcome data from both groups are neither normally distributed nor homogeneous, non-parametric statistical tests are used (such as the Mann-Whitney test) must be used for hypothesis testing, not parametric statistics (such as the t-test). With student learning results using the Mann-Whitney test, $Z_{\text{count}} = 2.94$ and the Z_{table} value at the 0.05 significance level is 1.96, which shows that the $Z_{\text{count}} > Z_{\text{table}}$ ($2.94 > 1.96$). This indicates that H_0

is rejected and H_1 is accepted, showing the Learning Cycle 7E model influences the learning outcomes of class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung on acids-bases material.

This learning carried out with two classes that were used as research samples. Model Learning Cycle 7E used to provide learning to the experimental group. Meanwhile, the direct learning model (Direct Instruction) was used for the control group. Each class has five meetings to carry out research: four meetings are held for the learning process to discuss one session is allocated for administering the post-test

According to the descriptive statistical analysis presented in Table 1, students in the experimental group achieved an average score of 78.11, with scores ranging from a high of 87.5 to a low of 41.66. In contrast, the control group had an average score of 72.40, with the same range of scores from 87.5 to 41.66. Table 2 shows that 68.75% of students in the experimental group (22 students) achieved higher learning outcomes, while 33.34% did not. This performance surpasses the control group. This is higher than the control group, where only 43.75% of students (14 students) completed, and 56.52% did not. These research findings are strengthened by previous research, such as research carried out by Widoratih et al (2016), that the learning model Learning Cycle 7E have an influence on improving student learning outcomes.

Figure 2The Phase of Learning Cycle 7E

Source: Bentley, Ebert & Ebert (in Laelasari, Subroto, & Ikhsan, 2014

The first phase is elicit (testing initial knowledge), This phase begins with the teacher

giving basic questions related to acid-base lessons using examples of acids-bases in everyday life. Example of a question: "Have you ever eaten oranges and bitter melon? How does it feel? Explain in your own words and according to your experience." The results of the students' answers were quite enthusiastic and all of them answered simultaneously correctly.

The second phase is engagement, (involving) in this phase the teacher builds students' interest in learning by focusing attention on students regarding the lesson they will learn. In this phase the teacher delivers demonstrations related to the material. For example: "Acids and bases are two chemical compounds that are very important in everyday life. Acids and bases are found in food, of course you often find food that tastes sour and bitter, right? If the food tastes sour then what is it? If food tastes bitter then what is it? Acid and base properties can be understood through various acid-base theories. In this session, students can share their thoughts and respond based on their knowledge. The students' answers are quite enthusiastic and answer questions from the teacher.

The third phase is exploration. In this phase, students are guided to formulate a problem formulation related to the demonstration that has been observed and draw conclusions on the problem formulation with the teacher and put it on the Student Worksheet (LKPD). In this phase, students carry out exploration by searching many learning sources in order to find answers to the problem formulation that has been created, discussing with their group friends to search for material from books and the internet according to the problem formulation that has been created.

Based on Figure 3, it can be seen that students are active when discussing with their group friends to search for material from books and the internet according to the problem formulation that has been created. Where the concept or material obtained is then written on the LKPD that is distributed, you can see it in Figure 4

Figure 3. Students Explore with Their Group Members

EXPLORE

Berdasarkan pernyataan di atas, buatlah rumusan masalah dan diskusikan bersama teman kelompokmu

1.) Bagaimana ciri-ciri asam dan basa
 - Ciri-ciri asam : - rasanya masam
 - dapat merubah warna indikator asam basa
 - pH kurang dari 7

- Ciri-ciri basa : - rasanya pahit dan licin alami
 - dapat merubah warna indikator asam basa
 - pH lebih dari 7

2.) contoh asam basa dalam kehidupan sehari-hari
 Contoh asam : - cuka dan perasan jeruk
 contoh basa : - sabun dan baking soda

3.) Perbedaan ketiga teori asam basa
 - Teori Arrhenius adalah substansi yang dilarutkan dalam air akan menghasilkan ion hidrogen (H^+) sedangkan basa adalah substansi yang saat dilarutkan dalam air akan menghasilkan ion hidroksida (OH^-)
 - Teori Bronsted Lowry adalah substansi yang dapat mendonorkan ion hidrogen (H^+), dalam teori ini air dapat bertindak sebagai asam atau basa
 - Teori Lewis adalah substansi yang dapat menerima pasangan elektron, sedangkan basa adalah substansi yang dapat mendonorkan pasangan elektron

Figure 4. Results of Problem Formulation and Answers that have been Written in the LKPD

The fourth phase is explanation, students from each group present the results of their research on the material studied.

Figure 5. Group Presentation

Figure 6. Students Ask Questions

After presenting the results of the group work (figures 5,6) students from other groups provided responses. This is because they get different understandings. Apart from that, some students ask questions that they think are not clear. The result is that students in this phase discuss, ask and answer and pay attention to the teacher

The fifth phase is elaboration. In this phase, students apply the concepts or material they have learned in the previous phase by answering questions or questions asked by the teacher. The teacher then provides additional explanations and ensures that students understand the material that day. In this phase, students pay attention to the progress of the discussion, questions and explanations from the teacher and students write them on the LKPD.

ELABORATE

Tuliskan hasil akhir atau kesimpulan yang kelompok kalian ketahui dari diskusi yang dilakukan

Figure 7. Phase Elaborate

The sixth phase is evaluation, students are seen focused on completing the quizzes in the LKPD based on the material they have learned. Students work on the quiz questions individually.

Next, the seventh phase is carried out, namely extend. In this phase, the teacher and students draw conclusions from that day's lesson. The teacher gives homework in the form of essay questions related to the material they have studied and outlines what will be discussed at the next meeting. Then at the next meeting, namely before the core learning is carried out, the teacher first presents the evaluation results of the previous meeting. The teacher and students review the evaluation results to confirm comprehension of the prior lesson.

Learning in both the experimental and control classes follows the planned model. In the experimental class, students using the 7E Learning Cycle model actively engage by asking questions, pay attention to the teacher's explanations and carry out group discussions regularly. Even during the research process, it cannot be denied that there were several obstacles. This is due to the researchers' limitations in teaching experience, especially in classroom management and educator communication in delivering material.

EVALUATION

Jawablah pertanyaan dibawah ini bersama kelompok kalian

1. Tuliskan sifat-sifat dari larutan asam dan basa!
2. Jelaskan pengertian asam dan basa menurut Arrhenius!
3. Jelaskan pengertian asam dan basa menurut Bronsted Lowry!
4. Jelaskan pengertian asam dan basa menurut Lewis!
5. Berikan masing-masing 1 contoh asam basa menurut Arrhenius, Bronsted Lowry dan Lewis!

Sifat² Asam :

- 1) --
 - Larutan asam memiliki rasa asam
 - Menghantarkan arus listrik
 - Reaksi dengan logam
 - merubah warna lakmus merah

Sifat² Basa :

- Rasa Pahit dan licin
- Menghantarkan arus listrik
- reaksi dgn lemak dan minyak
- Sifat pembebas Hidrogen.

2) Pengertian asam dan Basa Menurut Arrhenius !
 Asam adl zat yang dapat membebaskan ion hidrogen (H⁺) ketika larut : dalam air.
 basa adl/zat yang dapat membebaskan ion hidrogen (OH⁻) ketika larut dalam air.

3) pengertian asam dan basa menurut Bronsted-lowry
 asam adl/substansi yang dapat menyumbangkan ion hidrogen (H⁺) ke dalam larutan.
 basa adl/substansi yang dapat menerima ion hidrogen (H⁺) dalam larutan.

4) pengertian asam dan basa menurut Lewis
 asam adl/zat yang menerima atau menangkap pasangan elektron.
 basa adl/zat yang menyumbangkan atau memberikan pasangan elektron.

5) # Contoh Asam basa menurut Lewis :

$$\text{BF}_3 + \text{NH}_3 \rightarrow \text{NH}_3\text{BF}_3$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{F} \\ | \\ \text{F}-\text{B} \\ | \\ \text{F} \end{array} + \begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ | \\ \text{N}-\text{H} \\ | \\ \text{H} \end{array} \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \text{F} \\ | \quad | \\ \text{N}-\text{B} \\ | \quad | \\ \text{H} \quad \text{F} \end{array}$$

Asam Basa

Contoh Asam Basa menurut Arrhenius :

$$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{OH}^-$$

$\text{H}_1 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$ contoh menurut Bronsted Lowry
 Asam Basa

Figure 8. Evaluation Results of One of the Students

So, there were several participants who had not discussed well and seemed passive. To achieve effective learning, it is highly recommended that teachers be able to manage the class well and implement appropriate communication

strategies. A successful learning process requires strong collaboration between the teacher as facilitator and students as active participants. (Soleh, et al., 2009).

The inferential analysis showed that both the experimental and control group data came from populations with non-normal distributions, as indicated by the prerequisite test calculations. Additionally, the homogeneity test revealed that the variances of the experimental and control groups were not homogeneous. The Mann-Whitney test, a non-parametric statistical method, was used for hypothesis testing. The Z value (2.94) exceeded the Ztable value (1.96), showing that the 7E Learning Cycle model affects the acid-base learning outcomes of class XI MIA students at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung.

Conclusion

The research and hypothesis testing conclude that using the Learning Cycle 7E model in teaching chemistry, especially on acids and bases, is effective, positively affects students' learning outcomes. This conclusion is supported by the Mann-Whitney test, which shows a $Z_{\text{count}} > Z_{\text{table}}$ ($2,94 > 1,96$).

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